

SHORT NOTES

Light Scattering by Catechuic Acid Solution

J. N. Chakravarti and S. N. Mukherjee

Measurement of light, scattered by solutions of natural gums, has been shown to afford a means of studying the shape and molecular weight of these materials¹⁻³. The theoretical aspects as well as the experimental techniques of the light-scattering method for the study of macromolecules in solution have been widely investigated. This communication deals with the results obtained from the study of catechuic acid, a complex polysaccharide acid, obtained from gum Catechu.

Procedure.—The sample of catechuic acid was prepared from the whole gum by acidification with 0.1*N*-HCl. The gum acid was precipitated with ethanol and washed until it was free of HCl. The free acid was redissolved in water, electrolysed, and finally precipitated with ethanol in presence of KBr. The precipitate was washed with ethanol, followed by dry ether, and finally dried over P₂O₅ *in vacuo*.

The procedure for making the solution as well as its adequate clarification has been mentioned previously²⁻³. The experimental technique for the light-scattering measurements was also discussed²⁻³. Light used was of 436 mμ wave length.

The molecular weight was determined by plotting the values of HC/T for a series of concentrations, followed by extrapolation to zero concentration, and taking the reciprocal of the intercept, since

$$HC/T\rho_{90} = \frac{1}{M} + 2BC\rho_{90} \quad \dots \quad (1)$$

where $H = 32 \pi^3 n_0^2 [(n-n_0)/C]^2 / 3N\lambda^4$, C is the concentration of the solution in g./ml, M is the solute weight-average molecular weight, B is a constant, n is the refractive index of the solution and n_0 that of the solvent, λ is the wave length of the incident light in cm, N is the Avogadro number, and T , the absolute turbidity of the solution in excess of that of the solvent. The quantity $(n-n_0)$ is the refractive increment of the solution from that of the solvent and ρ_{90} is the particle-scattering factor at 90°.

It appears from Fig. 1 that when the concentration of catechuic acid in aqueous solution is very low, the plot exhibits a very high slope, but when the concentration is increased, the curve gradually flattens and becomes almost parallel to the x -axis. On

1. Veiss and Eggenberge, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 76, 1560.
2. Mukherjee and Deb, *this Journal*, 1962, 39, 833.
3. Deb and Mukherjee, unpublished.

account of this curvature in the lower concentration range, it was found difficult to extrapolate the values of HC/T to zero concentration. As is evident from Fig. 1 the extrapolation could be made easier if the light-scattering measurement be carried out in solution containing $0.02N$ -HCl. The molecular weight calculated from the intercept comes out to be 1.3×10^6 . Additional correction is necessary for dissymmetry (Z) of scattering as well as for depolarisation.

FIG. 1. Variation of HC/T with conc.

FIG. 2. Variation of Z with conc.

The dissymmetry values of catechuic acid in aqueous solution and in $0.02N$ -HCl were extrapolated to zero concentration (Fig. 2). It is evident that a considerable decrease in the dissymmetry values as well as the extrapolated values of the gum takes place on addition of HCl. On the assumption of a polydisperse random coil as the suitable model, the intrinsic dissymmetry in $0.02N$ -HCl was calculated for the correction factor and the molecular weight, after this correction, was found to be 3.9×10^6 . Additional correction for depolarisation effect (Cabanne's factor = 1.15 in this case) increases the molecular weight to 4.5×10^6 .

The dimension of the catechuic acid gum molecule in aqueous and in $0.02N$ -HCl can be calculated from the corresponding intrinsic dissymmetry values. It appears that the root-mean-square end-to-end distance of the macromolecules is 327μ in aqueous solution, whereas in $0.02N$ -HCl the value reduces to 257μ . The reduction of the molecular length in $0.02N$ -HCl may be due to suppression of the acidic dissociation of catechuic acid in presence of excess of H^+ ions. The decrease of charged groups in the molecular chain reduces repulsion between the units and thereby shortening in length occurs.